

Measurement Properties of the Generalized Anxiety Disorder 7 - Item Scale (GAD-7) across purposes and populations worldwide : protocol for a living systematic review

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GENERAL INFORMATION:

Type and method of the review: Systematic review and meta-analysis conducted following the COSMIN guideline for systematic reviews of PROMs, and the PRISMA-COSMIN guideline for reporting systematic reviews of outcome measurement instruments (OMIs).

Condition or domain being studied: This systematic review focuses on anxiety.

Language: English.

Country: France.

Funding sources/sponsors: This work is part of the COLIVE-MH project funded by Wellcome under contract number C-013403.

Conflicts of interest: All authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Ethical approval and consent to participate: This study synthesizes and analyzes data from already published studies, therefore ethical approval is not required.

Other registration details: None.

Dissemination plans: We plan to publish the review findings in a peer-reviewed journal.

Details of any existing review of the same topic by the same authors: None.

Current review status: Ongoing.

Additional information: None.

Protocol updated on 9th February 2026

Acknowledgement: We thank Jessie Cunningham, BA (Hons); MSt (The Hospital for Sick Children) for peer review of the submitted search strategy, and Catherine Auzimour for the project management.

1. Introduction

Numerous patient-reported outcome measures are used to assess anxiety in clinical and research settings; however, their measurement properties are often evaluated in isolation and reported heterogeneously, limiting comparability across instruments and the development of common metrics. This fragmentation complicates instrument selection for clinicians, researchers, and guideline developers and contributes to heterogeneity in anxiety measurement (Wall & Lee, 2022). The Generalized Anxiety Disorder 7-item scale (GAD-7), originally developed by Spitzer et al. (2006), has become one of the most widely used instruments in clinical and research settings (Kliem et al., 2025). Despite the growing body of literature evaluating the measurement properties of the GAD-7, evidence remains dispersed across studies and reviews that differ in scope, methodological quality, and reporting standards, making synthesis and interpretation challenging for end-users (Plummer et al., 2016). Such fragmentation can hinder clinicians, researchers, and guideline developers in identifying the most robust and up-to-date evidence to support informed use of the scale.

Moreover, as new validation studies continue to emerge across populations and settings, conventional static reviews risk becoming rapidly outdated, also often described as the 'evidence-practice' gap (Elliott et al., 2014). To address this, there is a need for a synthesis that applies an internationally recognised standard such as COSMIN (Mokkink et al., 2018) while evolving alongside the literature. Living evidence synthesis offers a methodological solution by enabling the continuous incorporation and appraisal of newly published data over time. Recent methodological frameworks further emphasise that coupling rigorous evidence synthesis with an interactive online platform can enhance transparency, usability, and knowledge translation for diverse stakeholders (Gosling et al., 2024; Gosling et al., 2025). Accordingly, this living systematic review is designed not only to synthesise and periodically update evidence on the measurement properties of the GAD-7, but also to function as a sustainable knowledge translation resource, addressing a critical gap in the long-term accessibility and practical utility of measurement evidence. By centralising these findings, this project will provide a robust and reliable guide for the scale's application across diverse global settings.

2. Methods

2.3. Objectives

The primary objective of this project is two fold: (i) to systematically identify, appraise, and synthesise all available evidence on the measurement properties, as defined by COSMIN, of the GAD-7 in measuring anxiety across purposes (e.g., outcome measure of treatment effect, screening) and populations worldwide, using a living evidence synthesis approach; and (ii) to disseminate this evidence through an open access, accessible, regularly updated web-based platform to support researchers, clinicians, people with lived experience and other interest-holders in the informed selection and use of the scale.

The secondary objectives are (i) to evaluate the feasibility of implementing the GAD-7 in clinical and research settings; (ii) to assess the interpretability of its scores; and (iii) to identify and highlight key research gaps.

This protocol is part of COLIVE-MH, a broader project designed to build a continuously updated platform on the measurement properties of four common measures in mental health, recommended by the Common Measures in Mental Health Science Initiative (CMMHS) (Farber et al., 2023): PHQ-9, the Generalized Anxiety Disorder 7 item scale (GAD-7), the World Health Organization Disability Assessment Schedule 2.0 (WHODAS 2.0), and the Revised Child Anxiety and Depression Scale 25 items (RCADS-25).. It follows the methodological framework described in the COLIVE-MH Master Protocol. The project involves international teams of researchers in clinical epidemiology, psychiatry, and anthropology and co-researchers with lived experience.

2.2. Study Design and Reporting Guidelines

The protocol of this systematic review follows the PRISMA-P (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses Protocols) guidelines (Moher et al., 2015) and will be prospectively registered on the Zenodo platform (<https://zenodo.org>). In line with recent guidance for living systematic reviews, the protocol also adheres to relevant items from the PRISMA-LSR extension, which provides reporting recommendations specific to the living mode (Akl et al., 2024). Protocol deviations and amendments will be transparently listed in the supplementary materials of future publications.

This protocol adheres to the PRESS guideline for peer review of electronic search strategies (McGowan et al., 2016), PRISMA-COSMIN for reporting systematic reviews of outcome measurement instruments (Elsman et al., 2024), QUADAS-2 for diagnostic accuracy studies where applicable, and GRIPP-2 for reporting patient and public involvement (Staniszewska et al., 2017).

2.3. Formulation of the research question

Construct: In the present review, we focus on studies using the GAD-7 to measure the construct it purports. The GAD-7 was developed to screen and measure generalized anxiety disorder (GAD) and anxiety symptoms as defined by DSM-IV criteria (Spitzer et al., 2006).

Population: There will be no restrictions on population characteristics. We will include all ages, genders, sex, nationalities, languages, countries, cultural backgrounds, and settings. This includes clinical (physical and mental health) and non-clinical populations. Evidence syntheses based on COSMIN guidelines will be conducted in given populations based on clinically sound and sociodemographically meaningful categories.

Type of instrument: Version of GAD-7 used (including adaptations made into different cultures and languages).

Measurement properties (based on the COSMIN framework, with adaptations):

1. Content validity
2. Structural validity
3. Internal consistency
4. Cross-cultural validity/measurement invariance
5. Reliability
6. Measurement error
7. Criterion validity
8. Diagnostic and screening accuracy
9. Hypothesis testing for construct validity
10. Responsiveness

Other properties:

11. Feasibility
12. Interpretability
13. Acceptability

Studies: Primary studies with any design (incl. Cross-sectional, cohort, validation and instrument development study, trials, qualitative studies) appraising at least one measurement property of the GAD-7 will be considered eligible.

2.4. Pilot screening and testing of the search strategy (GAD-7)

Before drafting the current protocol, we conducted a pilot study to evaluate the feasibility of the project and inform strategic decisions. An initial exploratory assessment was undertaken to evaluate the volume and nature of the literature related to the measurement properties of the GAD-7 and to support the development of a precise and feasible search strategy. Instrument-related terms were first tested in Google Scholar and PubMed to gauge the breadth of available literature (the results of this exploratory phase are presented in Table 2 in Appendix C). The pilot study allowed us to refine the search strings, eligibility criteria, and screening procedures.

2.5. Eligibility criteria

Studies will be included if they meet the following inclusion criteria:

1. Peer-reviewed empirical studies with at least one stated objective to examine one or more measurement properties of the GAD-7 when measuring anxiety, or studies reporting results on at least one measurement property of the GAD-7 in their methods or results sections.
 - a. The construct of interest is anxiety. Although the GAD-7 was originally developed to assess symptoms of generalised anxiety disorder, subsequent research has demonstrated that it has useful measurement properties for broader anxiety constructs, including other anxiety disorders and anxiety screening in the general population (Spitzer et al., 2006; Aktürk et al., 2025; also see Löwe et al., 2008).
 - b. Measurement properties will be defined according to the COSMIN taxonomy (Mokkink et al., 2010; Mokkink et al., 2024), with adaptations. Operational definitions of each property and their classification are provided in Table 1 and further operationalized in Appendix A. Any statistical methods of analysis will be included (e.g., classic test theory, item response theory).
2. No restrictions on population characteristics. We will include all ages, sexes/genders, countries, languages, cultural backgrounds, or settings, including clinical (physical and mental health) and non-clinical populations.
3. The original GAD-7 and any adaptations (cultural or population specific) will be eligible for inclusion only if the original item content of the instrument is retained (e.g., Icelandic GAD-7 (Beard & Bjorgvinsson, 2014); Korean GAD-7 (Seo & Park, 2015)). Modifications in the wording of items will also be allowed, as long as the meaning is not substantially changed. These modifications will be explicitly recorded and considered in the data extraction and synthesis.

4. Include all self-report formats, electronic, paper, or read-aloud of the GAD-7, as long as the participant is the main respondent, and there is no external judgment or influence beyond standard guidance. Populations with severe impairment will be included if individuals can independently understand, interpret, and respond to the GAD-7.
5. Primary studies of any design - including cross-sectional, longitudinal, cohort, validation, instrument development studies, and trials (randomized/non-randomized) - will be included only if they report data on the measurement properties of the GAD-7. Qualitative studies in which participants from any population (e.g., people with lived experience of depression, clinicians, caregivers, or members of the general population) will also be included if they report evidence on measurement properties (e.g., content validity, development paper) or other properties of the tool (e.g., acceptability, feasibility, interpretability). Eligibility will be determined by the presence of evaluable evidence on measurement properties rather than by study design alone.

Studies will be excluded if they meet the following exclusion criteria:

1. Non-peer-reviewed outputs, such as conference abstracts, posters, dissertations, and other short communications.
2. Studies in which the GAD-7 is used solely as a comparator to evaluate another instrument, or only as a predictor, grouping variable, or prevalence estimator, without any examination of the measurement properties of the GAD-7 itself, will be excluded.
3. Case studies will be excluded because they do not provide enough information to evaluate measurement properties.

In addition to the previous exclusion criteria, we will also apply the following exclusion criteria, but these studies will be systematically identified and tagged under predefined categories during the entire screening process, from title and abstract to full-text selection.

1. Potential Clinician-Reported Outcome Measure (ClinROM) and the Observer-Reported Outcome Measure (ObsROM) versions of GAD-7 will be excluded if they were used to capture the perspective or experience of clinicians/observers, rather than the respondents.
2. Studies investigating the effects of administering the GAD-7 on individuals, groups, or settings, such as psychological impact, behavioral consequences, or social effects. These studies focus on the consequences of measurement rather

than on examining measurement properties. These studies will be tagged for inclusion in a separate scoping review.

3. Studies providing conceptual, methodological, or implementation-oriented insights into the use of the GAD-7, for example, studies examining barriers and facilitators to uptake, training strategies for clinicians, or integration of the GAD-7 into routine care or digital systems. They will be used to guide the website interface of the platform.
4. Studies using the GAD-7 alongside other measures to generate crosswalks, linking functions, or score equivalence across instruments. The primary focus of these studies is on mathematical comparability across scales rather than on examining the measurement performance of the GAD-7 itself (e.g., a score of 8 on the GAD-7 = a score of 10 on another anxiety or distress scale).
5. Studies examining shortened or extended versions of the GAD-7 in which the content of the original items has been modified, for example. This includes modifications to response options (e.g., alternative response formats), scoring algorithms (e.g., alternative ways of summing the items into a total score), cut-off thresholds (e.g., exploring different thresholds than the originally validated), instructions for completion (e.g., more developed or specific instructions than the originally provided) or recall period (e.g., experience in the last week instead of the last two weeks).
6. Studies in which the GAD-7 is used to measure a construct that is different from anxiety or insufficiently specified.
7. Systematic reviews and meta-analyses of the measurement properties of the GAD-7 will be excluded from the systematic synthesis stage. However, they will be identified and tagged during the mapping stage. For example, systematic reviews summarizing measurement evidence on the GAD-7, either alone or in comparison with other measures (such as anxiety). These reviews will not be included as primary evidence synthesis but will be tagged to cross-check coverage of primary studies and to support identification of additional eligible studies.

Table 1

Definitions of measurement properties and other properties of the measurement tool.

Measurement properties and other properties of the tools	Definition
1. <i>Content validity</i>	The degree to which the content of a PROM is an adequate reflection of the construct to be measured.
2. <i>Structural validity</i>	The degree to which the scores of a PROM are an adequate reflection of the dimensionality of the construct to be measured.
3. <i>Internal consistency</i>	The degree of the interrelatedness among the items.
4. <i>Cross-cultural validity/measurement invariance</i>	The degree to which the performance of the items on a translated or culturally adapted PROM is an adequate reflection of the performance of the items of the original version of the PROM.
5. <i>Reliability</i>	The proportion of the total variance in the measurements that is due to 'true' difference between respondents. It indicates an instrument's ability to distinguish between individuals—with various scores and despite measurement error (Mokkink et al., 2023; 2026).
6. <i>Measurement error</i>	The systematic and random error of a patient's score that is not attributed to true changes in the construct to be measured. It refers to how similar or close the scores are from repeated measurements in an individual who is stable on the outcome of interest (Mokkink et al., 2023; 2026).
7. <i>Criterion validity</i>	The degree to which the scores of a PROM are an adequate reflection of a 'gold standard.'
8. <i>Diagnostic and screening accuracy</i>	The ability of the PROM to correctly classify study participants, as having the target disorder or not. In most cases, that information will be relevant when the PROM is considered for diagnostic reasons, i.e., to identify the disorder that most likely is responsible for the signs and symptoms of the patient, or for screening purposes (to identified patients with unrecognised anxiety)
9. <i>Hypothesis testing for construct validity</i>	The degree to which the scores of a PROM are consistent with hypotheses (regarding relationships to scores of other instruments or differences between relevant groups) based on the assumption that the PROM validly measures the construct to be measured.
10. <i>Responsiveness</i>	The ability of a PROM to detect change over time in the construct to be measured.
11. <i>Feasibility²</i>	Ease of application of the PROM in its intended context of use, given constraints such as time or money.
12. <i>Interpretability²</i>	The degree to which one can assign qualitative meaning - that is, clinical or commonly understood connotations – to a PROM's quantitative scores or change in scores.
13. <i>Acceptability²</i>	How respondents perceive the experience of completing the scale, e.g., perceived intrusiveness, burden, potential harms or benefits.

Notes: The definitions of the measurement properties are based on the COSMIN taxonomy, extracted from the COSMIN 2.0 guidelines (Mokkink et al., 2024). The Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Diagnostic Test Accuracy will be used where appropriate to supplement the COSMIN guidance (Deeks et al., 2023).

¹The word 'true' must be seen in the context of the CTT, which states that any observation is composed of two components – a true score and error associated with the observation. 'True' is the average score that would be obtained if the scale were given an infinite number of times. It refers only to the consistency of the score, and not to its accuracy (Streiner & Norman, 2008).

² Feasibility and interpretability are not considered a measurement property, but an important aspect when selecting measurement instruments. Acceptability was added specifically to this project and the definition will be refined according to the literature identified during the systematic review.

2.6. Information sources and search strategy

To identify relevant studies, we will conduct systematic searches in 5 major bibliographic databases: MEDLINE via PubMed, CINAHL via EBSCO, Embase via Elsevier, Web of Science via Clarivate, and PsycInfo via EBSCO. Grey literature will not be searched. Although grey literature can provide relevant content to increase the comprehensiveness of a review and reduce publication bias, the systematic review aims to map and synthesize peer reviewed studies only to ensure the feasibility and quality of the overall project. We acknowledge that restricting inclusion to peer-reviewed literature may result in the omission of locally produced knowledge, rare language adaptations, and context-specific validation studies that are not indexed in major international bibliographic databases.

The searches will be conducted from 1st January 1995 until 20th January 2026. As GAD-7 is a part of the COLIVE-MH project, the lower bound chosen is based on the data available for the other two scales (i.e., PHQ-9 and WHODAS II), to allow a sufficient margin prior to the first development papers of the PHQ-9 and WHODAS-II. An update of the searches will be conducted 6 months after the initial search and thereafter updated every 3 months.

The search strategy is structured around two main concept blocks: (1) the GAD-7 and (2) measurement properties. These blocks will be combined using the Boolean operator AND. The measurement properties block is based on a validated search filter developed by the COSMIN group to identify studies on measurement properties (Terwee et al., 2009; <https://www.cosmin.nl/tools/pubmed-search-filters/>), which was supplemented with additional keywords across all measurement properties. Database-specific subject headings (such as MeSH, Emtree) and syntax were used where applicable.

The review team initially developed the search strategy. It was then reviewed and translated for all bibliographic databases by two information specialists from

Université Paris Cité, France. Finally, the full search strategy underwent independent peer review by an external information specialist from the Hospital for Sick Children, Toronto, Canada, in accordance with the PRESS 2015 guidelines (McGowan et al., 2016), before execution. The search strategies are provided in Appendix B.

In addition, the reference lists of included primary studies and relevant systematic reviews will be screened to identify any additional eligible studies. Citation tracking tools (e.g., Research Rabbit <https://www.researchrabbit.ai/>) may also be used to identify related studies, including forward and backward citations of included articles.

2.7. Screening procedure

Records will be imported into the Sustainable Knowledge (SK) platform developed by Epistemonikos as part of its end-to-end system for deduplication and reference management (Rada et al., 2020; <https://www.skplatform.org>). The platform will also be used for the screening process. Two independent reviewers will conduct title and abstract screening. Discrepancies will be resolved by a third reviewer. Only records for which eligibility cannot be determined at the title and abstract stage after discussion will proceed to full-text assessment.

These full-text records will be screened to determine final eligibility and to arrive at the set of studies included in the systematic review. Articles excluded at the full-text stage, along with reasons for exclusion, will be logged in a table. Disagreements regarding study eligibility at the full-text stage will be resolved through discussion between the two reviewers; if consensus cannot be reached, a third reviewer will be consulted. A PRISMA flow diagram will be used to document the study selection process.

2.8. Sequential approach for data extraction and synthesis

To achieve this objective, the project will be organized in two sequential and complementary phases : (1) **Phase A—living mapping of evidence** - systematically identifies all studies that report one or more measurement properties of the GAD-7, classifying their characteristics (study features, instrument characteristics, participant characteristics, and measurement properties assessed). The mapped evidence will be fed into the living platform and updated regularly. (2) **Phase B - evidence syntheses of the measurement properties** - conducts COSMIN-guided systematic reviews on specific populations and intended instrument uses. Each review will synthesize results,

assess risk of bias, grade the certainty of evidence. These syntheses will be generated by the living platform in an integrated format that will allow the evidence to be combined and compared across contexts. In addition, we will identify potential areas for improvement of the GAD-7.

Phase A - Living mapping of the evidence

Data extraction. All studies meeting the inclusion criteria after full-text screening will undergo structured data extraction within the Epistemonikos end-to-end system. All the reviewers involved in the screening will be trained, and reviewers will independently extract data for at least 10% for alignment among reviewers. The codebook for data extraction for the Living Mapping phase is provided in Appendix D. For each study, data will be collected across eight broad categories:

- A. **Study metadata:** Study ID, year of publication, journal, DOI, etc.
- B. **Study characteristics:** Design of the study, inclusion criteria with threshold, etc.
- C. **Characteristics of the GAD-7:** exact version of the instrument used, administration mode (self-administered, read-aloud, etc.), format (paper/pencil, online, etc.), different languages and cultural adaptations (e.g., translated to Arabic), or other adaptations (e.g., adolescent version).
- D. **Purpose of use** for which the properties of the GAD-7 are being examined (outcome assessment, screening/diagnostic).
- E. **Participant characteristics:** sociodemographic (age, gender/sex, and country; specific demographics such as prisoners, migrants, etc.) and clinical characteristics (e.g., general population, physical illness, mental health condition).
- F. **Measurement properties** will be classified based on the analyses and statistics reported in the primary studies, following COSMIN guidance. Definitions of all measurement properties are listed in Table 1, and examples of commonly reported analyses and indicators are operationalized in Appendix A.

G. Other properties of the tool: Studies reporting evidence on the feasibility, interpretability, and acceptability of the GAD-7 will also be classified accordingly.

H. Involvement of contributors with lived experiences: We will extract information on whether individuals with lived experiences actively contributed, beyond the role of a participant, to each study included.

The data extraction form will be pilot-tested on a subset of random included studies to ensure completeness and consistency. In the context of a living systematic review, both the extraction form and the dataset will be updated on an ongoing basis as new evidence emerges.

Data synthesis. The data extraction of this phase will allow us to map the available evidence and to inform the organization of Phase B. The data will be analyzed with descriptive statistics, and all outputs will be displayed in the open-access platform.

Phase B—Living evidence syntheses of the GAD-7 measurement properties

Phase B will conduct evidence syntheses on GAD-7 measurement properties using COSMIN methodology. We begin by analyzing characteristics from the GAD-7's original development studies to establish its measurement scope and inform content validity evaluation.

Drawing from Phase A living evidence mapping results, we will perform targeted COSMIN-guided systematic reviews for different populations and intended instrument use (e.g., GAD-7 properties in older adults with comorbidities). Sequence of the reviews conduct will integrate mapped evidence availability, scientific expertise, and lived experts advice, maintaining methodological consistency across reviews.

For each review, we will systematically extract data on all reported measurement properties and other characteristics (e.g., interpretability) of the GAD-7, evaluate methodological quality of included studies, apply COSMIN criteria to assess property quality, synthesize results (including quantitative synthesis where appropriate), and assess evidence certainty using GRADE. Adapting and refining both the COSMIN risk of bias checklist and GRADE criteria for certainty of synthesised

evidence are part of the present project. These projects will be detailed in other research protocols.

Detailed synthesis procedures are outlined in the COLIVE-MH Master Protocol.

3. Living systematic review methodology

This review is designed as a living systematic review. Following the initial search, literature searches will be updated after 6 months to allow enough time for the initial screening and data extraction, and then at subsequent intervals of 3 months. However, frequency of updates may be adapted based on the amount of evidence and the available resources. At each update, newly identified records will undergo title and abstract screening, full-text assessment, data extraction, and appraisal using the same eligibility criteria and standardized methodological procedures as those applied in the initial review. Data synthesis, analysis, and certainty-of-evidence assessment will be updated at the same 3-month intervals. Every update will be disseminated in partnership through the Epistemonikos Platform for Interactive Evidence Synthesis (<https://www.skplatform.org>).

The review is planned to remain in living mode for a period of 2 years starting from the date of the first search. Retirement from the living mode will be considered based on prespecified criteria including stability of conclusions across updates, or reduced relevance of the review question. If none of these criteria are met at the end of the planned period, the need for continuing the updates will be reassessed.

4. Ethics and Dissemination

As this study synthesizes existing literature, no ethical approval will be required. The protocol will be prospectively registered on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>), with all deviations transparently reported. Findings will be disseminated through peer-reviewed publications and national and international conference presentations. Results will be hosted on an open-access living evidence platform, the development of which will be described elsewhere.

5. Lived experience engagement

We consider the engagement of people with lived experiences of mental health conditions/disorders as key to this project since the GAD-7 and the three other

measurement tools are PROMS intending to measure mental health symptoms through, i.e., self-reported evaluation of symptoms. As of 9th February 2026, the engagement plan is still under development with people with lived experiences from different countries and with different backgrounds. This protocol has been developed with co-researchers with lived experiences and backgrounds in psychology and is under review by three lived experts with backgrounds in anthropology. The next update of this protocol will display the precise procedures of engagement at each stage of the LSR.

6. Conclusion

This systematic review protocol will provide a rigorous and transparent framework for the continuous appraisal of the GAD-7's measurement properties. By adopting a living evidence approach, the project will overcome the limitations of static reviews, ensuring that evidence remains current as new validation studies emerge globally. The resulting open-access platform will serve as a sustainable knowledge translation tool, providing clinicians and researchers with a high-quality, up-to-date evidence base to support the informed use of the GAD-7 in diverse clinical and research settings.

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Appendix A

Operationalization of the Measurement Properties across the Project

The table below provides operational definitions of each measurement property considered in COLIVE-MH, together with practical guidance for reviewers on how to identify relevant evidence in primary studies. For each property, we specify its conceptual definition and indicate the types of analyses, statistics, or study features that reviewers should look for (but not limited to) when extracting and classifying evidence on measurement properties. We also included other properties of the measurement tools that are not measurement properties but constitute important aspects when using a tool (i.e., feasibility, interpretability, acceptability). These definitions do not take into account the context of use (population, purpose) of the measure and are theoretical. Nevertheless, we acknowledge that measurement properties are the product of an interaction between a measurement tool and a population, meaning that these properties might vary across populations. For instance, convergent validity might be correct in a sample of people with diagnosed depression but not in a sample of people with no mental health disorders. The definitions and operationalizations are based on the COSMIN guidelines, which are the most comprehensive framework we identified (Mokkink, Elsman, & Terwee, 2024). However, we acknowledge that measurement science is a dynamic field and that alternative definitions, methods, and further progress can be made to conceptualize, assess, and interpret measurement properties.

Measurement (and other related) properties	Definitions and Operationalization
1. Content validity	<p>Definition: Content validity is the degree to which the content of an instrument adequately reflects the construct to be measured. It comprises three aspects: relevance (whether items are pertinent to the construct and population), comprehensiveness (whether all key aspects of the construct are covered), and comprehensibility (whether items, instructions, response options, and recall period are understood as intended).</p> <p>Typical indicators: Content validity evidence may come from concept elicitation studies (e.g., qualitative interviews or focus groups) assessing whether all key concepts are represented; from pilot or cognitive interviewing studies assessing comprehensibility of items, instructions, response options, and recall period; or from separate content validity studies in which people with lived experiences or professionals judge relevance, comprehensiveness, and comprehensibility. Analyses may include, e.g., content analysis, framework analysis, deductive analysis, or grounded theory.</p>

2. Structural validity	<p>Definition: Structural validity refers to the degree to which the scores of a PROM adequately reflect the dimensionality of the construct to be measured, that is, whether the items group into the expected factor structure or latent model.</p> <p>Typical indicators: Structural validity is commonly evaluated using exploratory or confirmatory factor analysis (EFA, CFA), principal component analysis (PCA), item response theory (IRT), or Rasch models. Reported results may include the number of factors, item–factor loadings, explained variance, eigenvalues, model fit indices (e.g., CFI, TLI, RMSEA, SRMR), and tests of model assumptions such as unidimensionality, local independence, monotonicity, or item fit statistics.</p>
3. Internal consistency	<p>Definition: Internal consistency refers to the degree of interrelatedness among items in a scale. It reflects whether items consistently measure the same underlying construct, assuming unidimensionality.</p> <p>Typical indicators: Internal consistency is typically quantified using Cronbach’s alpha, McDonald’s Omega, or IRT/Rasch-based reliability indices (e.g., standard error of theta). Interpretation of these statistics requires evidence that the items form a unidimensional scale, which should be established through prior assessment of structural validity.</p>
4. Cross-cultural validity/measurement invariance	<p>Definition: Cross-cultural validity (or measurement invariance) refers to the extent to which PROM items perform equivalently across different groups, such as languages, cultures, genders, age groups, or clinical populations. It assesses whether individuals with the same underlying level of the construct respond similarly to the items, regardless of group membership.</p> <p>Typical indicators: Cross-cultural validity is commonly evaluated using multi-group factor analysis, including tests of configural, metric, and scalar invariance, or through differential item functioning (DIF) analyses. Studies may also examine longitudinal measurement invariance to assess score comparability over time. Comparisons typically involve culturally or linguistically distinct groups but may also include other relevant subgroups.</p>
5. Reliability	<p>Definition: Reliability refers to the proportion of total variance in scores that is due to true differences between individuals. It reflects the ability of an instrument to distinguish between respondents.</p>

	<p>Typical indicators: Reliability is evaluated using repeated measurements in participants who are expected/assumed to remain stable on the construct. Measurements should be conducted under identical conditions, including the same PROM version, administration mode, response format, and setting, except for the specific source of variation being examined. Most commonly, reliability is assessed over time (test–retest reliability), but studies may also examine consistency across administration modes (e.g., paper vs digital), response formats (e.g., Likert vs VAS), or administrators (e.g., self-report vs interviewer-administered). Reported statistics typically include intraclass correlation coefficients (ICC) or kappa values, with specification of the ICC model when applicable. Some studies report Pearson or Spearman correlations, although these are less appropriate for assessing reliability.</p>
6. Measurement error	<p>Definition: Measurement error refers to the systematic and random error in a PROM score that is not attributable to true change in the construct being measured. It refers to the precision of the score. Measurement error is sometimes referred to as "agreement" and is evaluated using repeated measurements in participants who are assumed to be stable on the construct. The same data collected for the assessment of reliability can be used to evaluate measurement error.</p> <p>Typical indicators: Measurement error is assessed using repeated measurements in stable participants, often drawing on the same study designs used for reliability analyses. Reported statistics may include the standard error of measurement (SEM), smallest detectable change (SDC), limits of agreement (LoA), or percentage agreement for categorical scores. These indices quantify the amount of error around an observed score or change score. Kappa statistics are not measures of measurement error but of reliability.</p>
7. Criterion validity	<p>Definition: Criterion validity refers to the degree to which PROM scores are an adequate reflection of a reference standard (gold standard).</p> <p>Definition by the review team: Upon discussion within the review team, we define as gold standard the reporting of symptom counts derived from clinical diagnostic interviews such as the Structured Clinical Interview for DSM (SCID) or the Mini International Neuropsychiatric Interview (MINI), which evaluate the same anxiety symptoms covered by the GAD-7. These symptom counts provide the most appropriate comparator for self-reported anxiety measurement.</p> <p>Psychiatric diagnoses are inherently clinical, requiring clinician-patient interaction and consideration of functional impairment, symptom duration, and exclusion of medical mimics. GAD-7 cut-off thresholds should not be used</p>

	<p>independently for diagnosing generalized anxiety disorder, as they omit these essential diagnostic components (Plummer et al., 2016; Rutter & Brown, 2017). Instead, GAD-7 thresholds serve as screening tools to identify individuals needing comprehensive clinical evaluation. Consequently, formal diagnosis does not constitute a suitable gold standard for GAD-7 criterion validity. The screening performance of GAD-7 thresholds for probable anxiety disorders is addressed on a separate measurement property (8. Diagnostic accuracy).</p>
<p>8. Diagnostic and screening accuracy</p>	<p>Definition by the review team: The review team will consider the accuracy of the GAD-7 when evaluated for both diagnostic (diagnosis of the disorder causing the symptoms in clinical population) and screening (identifying unrecognised disorder in non-clinical population) purposes.</p> <p>Diagnostic and screening accuracy can be defined as the ability of a PROM to correctly classify study participants based on the results, as having the disorder or not (Deeks & Bossuyt, 2023, Chapter 2).</p> <p>Typical indicators We will include studies examining the test accuracy of the GAD-7 against a binary diagnostic outcome, defined using a structured or semi-structured clinical interview based on established diagnostic criteria (e.g., DSM or ICD). Typical indicators of diagnostic accuracy are: sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive values, likelihood ratios, diagnostic odds ratios, area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC), and 2x2 classification tables. Studies may assess one or multiple cut-off values to examine classification performance across thresholds, often using ROC analyses.</p>
<p>9. Hypothesis testing for construct validity</p>	<p>Definition: Hypothesis testing for construct validity evaluates whether PROM scores behave as expected in relation to other measures or groups, based on a priori hypotheses defined by the review team.</p> <p>Hypotheses formulated by the review team: In the section of hypothesis testing for construct validity, the GAD-7 is assessed within the purpose of evaluating severity and hypotheses are formulated accordingly.</p> <p>Using GAD-7 as a measure of symptom severity Phase A will map the studies reporting on construct validity, providing an overview of the comparator instruments used. We expect that for convergent validity, the most common comparators will be ClinROMs like Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HAM-A) and clinician-rated GAD scales (FDA-recommended equivalents), and widely used PROMs such as Beck Anxiety Inventory (BAI), State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI), Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale-Anxiety subscale (HADS-A), and Penn State Worry Questionnaire (PSWQ), identified by previous validation studies and reviews (Spitzer et al., 2006; Löwe et al., 2008; Kroenke et al., 2016; Dhira et al., 2021).</p>

	<p>Further hypotheses for testing construct validity will be specified after the mapping step based on available comparators. We will consider further evidence synthesis (Phase B) on convergent, divergent, and discriminant validity depending on research community needs and available data, discussed with lived experience team members and clinicians. Usual indicators will be correlations between GAD-7 total scores and comparator measures.</p>
<p>10. Responsiveness</p>	<p>Definition: Responsiveness refers to the ability of a PROM to detect change over time in the construct to be measured. It concerns the accuracy of a change score in relation to a change in the construct measured.</p> <p>Typical indicators: Responsiveness is evaluated by testing a priori hypotheses about expected patterns of change, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Associations between change scores on the PROM and change scores on comparator instruments measuring the same or related constructs. • Differences in change between groups are expected to differ over time (e.g., intervention vs control groups, responders vs non-responders). • Expected effect sizes following interventions with known or established effects. <p>Hypotheses should specify the expected direction and, where possible, the expected magnitude of change or association. Reported results may include correlations between change scores, mean differences in change, or effect sizes. Statistical significance alone is not sufficient; emphasis is placed on whether observed changes align with predefined hypotheses. Measures such as Guyatt's responsiveness ratio or MIC/MID are not used to evaluate responsiveness itself, these are measures of interpretability.</p> <p>Hypotheses formulated by the review team:</p> <p>Hypotheses are based on the expected direction and magnitude of change scores in the GAD-7 compared to change scores in other instruments: We expect moderate-to-strong correlations between change scores on the GAD-7 and change scores on established measurements of anxiety (as a diagnosis or as a continuous measure of symptom severity). We expect that the comparator instruments most commonly found will be the same as those for construct validity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GAD-7 used for screening or diagnostic purposes: Diagnostic reference standard (e.g., with SCID, MINI, or DSM/ICD-based diagnosis). • GAD-7 for assessing symptom severity: Other validated measures (PROMs and ClinROMs) commonly used in clinical research for evaluating symptom severity, such as the HAM-A, clinician-rated GAD scales, PHQ-9, BAI, STAI, HADS-A, PSWQ.

	<p>Phase A will map the studies reporting on responsiveness, providing an overview of the comparator instruments used. Definitive hypotheses for responsiveness will be specified after the mapping step based on the available comparators. As for hypothesis testing for construct validity, we will synthesize evidence for responsiveness (Phase B) for the most used comparators, based on the needs of the research community and upon discussion with the members of the COLIVE-MH team.</p>
11. Feasibility	<p>Definition: Feasibility refers to the ease of administering the PROM in its intended context, considering practical constraints such as time, burden, cost, and accessibility.</p> <p>Typical indicators: Evidence on feasibility may be reported in studies describing the practical use of the PROM, including information on completion time, number of items, mode of administration, availability of translations, licensing or permission requirements, and implementation-related constraints. Some studies may also report indicators of acceptability or uptake.</p>
12. Interpretability	<p>Definition: Interpretability refers to the degree to which meaningful qualitative information can be assigned to PROM scores or change scores. Interpretability does not evaluate measurement quality itself but provides context for understanding what specific scores or changes represent.</p> <p>Typical indicators: Studies may report the distribution of scores, including floor and ceiling effects, reference values, or cut-off scores indicating severity levels (e.g., mild, moderate, severe). For change scores, studies may report minimal important change (MIC) or minimal important difference (MID), representing the smallest within-person change considered important. Although MIC/MID values are primarily used to interpret change, they are also necessary when evaluating measurement error.</p>
13. Acceptability	<p>Definition: How respondents perceive the experience of completing the scale, e.g., perceived intrusiveness, burden, potential harms, or benefits.</p> <p>Typical indicators: Time of completion, number of missing responses, satisfaction with the questionnaire, qualitative reports on the experience of using the scale in research or clinical settings, etc.</p>

Appendix B

Search strings

- **Block 1 (Instrument)**

("GAD scale"[Title/Abstract] OR "GAD assessment"[Title/Abstract] OR "GAD questionnaire"[Title/Abstract] OR "GAD-7"[Title/Abstract] OR "GAD7"[Title/Abstract] OR "GAD 7"[Title/Abstract] OR "GAD seven"[Title/Abstract] OR "General* Anxiety Disorder scale"[Title/Abstract] OR "General* Anxiety Disorder assessment"[Title/Abstract] OR "General* Anxiety Disorder questionnaire"[Title/Abstract] OR "general* anxiety disorder 7"[Title/Abstract] OR "general* anxiety disorder seven"[Title/Abstract] OR "GAD-2"[Title/Abstract] OR "GAD2"[Title/Abstract] OR "GAD 2"[Title/Abstract] OR "GAD two"[Title/Abstract] OR "general* anxiety disorder 2"[Title/Abstract] OR "general* anxiety disorder two"[Title/Abstract])

- **Block 2 (COSMIN filter + Librarian suggested (diagnostic accuracy) filter)**

(instrumentation[sh] OR methods[sh] OR "Validation Study"[pt] OR "Comparative Study"[pt] OR "Psychometrics"[MeSH Terms] OR psychometr*[tiab] OR clinimetr*[tw] OR clinometr*[tw] OR "Outcome Assessment, Health Care"[MeSH Terms] OR "outcome assessment"[tiab] OR "outcome measure"[tw] OR "observer variation"[MeSH Terms] OR "observer variation"[tiab] OR "Health Status Indicators"[MeSH Terms] OR "reproducibility of results"[MeSH Terms] OR reproducib*[tiab] OR "discriminant analysis"[MeSH Terms] OR reliab*[tiab] OR unreliab*[tiab] OR valid*[tiab] OR "coefficient of variation"[tiab] OR coefficient[tiab] OR homogeneity[tiab] OR homogeneous[tiab] OR "internal consistency"[tiab] OR (cronbach*[tiab] AND (alpha[tiab] OR alphas[tiab])) OR (item[tiab] AND (correlation*[tiab] OR selection*[tiab] OR reduction*[tiab])) OR agreement[tw] OR precision[tw] OR imprecision[tw] OR "precise values"[tw] OR test-retest[tiab] OR (test[tiab] AND retest[tiab]) OR (reliab*[tiab] AND (test[tiab] OR retest[tiab])) OR stability[tiab] OR interrater[tiab] OR inter-rater[tiab] OR intrarater[tiab] OR intra-rater[tiab] OR intertester[tiab] OR inter-tester[tiab] OR intratester[tiab] OR intra-tester[tiab] OR interobserver[tiab] OR inter-observer[tiab] OR intraobserver[tiab] OR intra-observer[tiab] OR intertechnician[tiab] OR inter-technician[tiab] OR intratechnician[tiab] OR intra-technician[tiab] OR interexaminer[tiab] OR inter-examiner[tiab] OR intraexaminer[tiab] OR intra-examiner[tiab] OR interassay[tiab] OR inter-assay[tiab] OR intraassay[tiab] OR intra-assay[tiab] OR interindividual[tiab] OR inter-individual[tiab] OR intraindividual[tiab] OR intra-individual[tiab] OR interparticipant[tiab] OR inter-participant[tiab] OR intraparticipant[tiab] OR intra-participant[tiab] OR kappa[tiab] OR kappas[tiab] OR repeatab*[tw] OR ((replicab*[tw] OR repeated[tw]) AND (measure[tw] OR measures[tw] OR findings[tw] OR result[tw] OR results[tw] OR test[tw] OR tests[tw])) OR generaliza*[tiab] OR generalisa*[tiab] OR concordance[tiab] OR (intraclass[tiab] AND correlation*[tiab]) OR discriminative[tiab] OR "known group"[tiab] OR "factor analysis"[tiab] OR "factor analyses"[tiab] OR "factor structure"[tiab] OR "factor structures"[tiab] OR dimension*[tiab] OR subscale*[tiab] OR (multitrait[tiab] AND scaling[tiab] AND (analysis[tiab] OR analyses[tiab])) OR "item discriminant"[tiab] OR "interscale

correlation*[tiab] OR error[tiab] OR errors[tiab] OR "individual variability"[tiab] OR "interval variability"[tiab] OR "rate variability"[tiab] OR (variability[tiab] AND (analysis[tiab] OR values[tiab])) OR (uncertainty[tiab] AND (measurement[tiab] OR measuring[tiab])) OR "standard error of measurement"[tiab] OR sensitiv*[tiab] OR responsive*[tiab] OR (limit[tiab] AND detection[tiab]) OR "minimal detectable concentration"[tiab] OR interpretab*[tiab] OR ((minimal[tiab] OR minimally[tiab] OR clinical[tiab] OR clinically[tiab]) AND (important[tiab] OR significant[tiab] OR detectable[tiab]) AND (change[tiab] OR difference[tiab])) OR (small*[tiab] AND (real[tiab] OR detectable[tiab]) AND (change[tiab] OR difference[tiab])) OR "meaningful change"[tiab] OR "ceiling effect"[tiab] OR "floor effect"[tiab] OR "Item response model"[tiab] OR IRT[tiab] OR Rasch[tiab] OR "Differential item functioning"[tiab] OR DIF[tiab] OR "computer adaptive testing"[tiab] OR "item bank"[tiab] OR "cross-cultural equivalence"[tiab]

OR "index test*[tiab] OR "reference test*[tiab] OR "reference standard*[tiab] OR "gold standard"[tiab] OR "structured clinical interview"[tiab] OR "diagnostic accuracy"[tiab~2] OR "DTA"[tiab] OR "predictive value*[tiab] OR "PPV"[tiab] OR "NPV"[tiab] OR "positive predictive value"[tiab] OR "negative predictive value"[tiab] OR "likelihood ratio*[tiab] OR "sensitivity"[ti] OR "specificity"[ti] OR "cut-off"[tiab] OR "cutoff"[tiab] OR "cut point"[tiab] OR "threshold score*[tiab] OR "ROC"[tiab] OR "receiver* operating characteristic*[tiab] OR "AUC"[tiab] OR "area* under the curve"[tiab] OR "case detection"[tiab] OR "case finding"[tiab] OR "classification*[tiab])

- **Block 3 (Publication block)**

NOT ("address"[Publication Type] OR "biography"[Publication Type] OR "case reports"[Publication Type] OR "comment"[Publication Type] OR "directory"[Publication Type] OR "editorial"[Publication Type] OR "festschrift"[Publication Type] OR "interview"[Publication Type] OR "lecture"[Publication Type] OR "legal case"[Publication Type] OR "legislation"[Publication Type] OR "letter"[Publication Type] OR "news"[Publication Type] OR "newspaper article"[Publication Type] OR "patient education handout"[Publication Type] OR "popular work"[Publication Type] OR "congress"[Publication Type] OR "consensus development conference"[Publication Type] OR "consensus development conference, nih"[Publication Type] OR "practice guideline"[Publication Type])

NOT ("animals"[MeSH Terms] NOT "humans"[MeSH Terms])

- **Block 4: Time limits**

AND ("1995/01/01"[Date - Publication] : "2026/01/20"[Date - Publication])

Reference for the COSMIN filter:

Terwee, C. B., Jansma, E. P., Riphagen, I. I., & de Vet, H. C. (2009). Development of a methodological PubMed search filter for finding studies on measurement properties of measurement instruments. *Quality of Life Research*, 18(8), 1115-1123.

Appendix C

Pilot screening and testing of the search strategy (GAD-7)

Purpose of the pilot study:

To refine the methodology of the living systematic review, we conducted a pilot study focused on assessing the feasibility of identifying and screening evidence on the measurement properties of GAD-7. The pilot was designed to evaluate the feasibility of the search strategy, screening workflow, and inclusion/exclusion criteria, guided by COSMIN recommendations. Before finalising the search strategy, an initial exploratory phase was conducted to assess the volume and nature of the literature related to the GAD-7. Instrument-related terms were first tested in Google Scholar and PubMed to evaluate the breadth of available studies and to inform the development of a precise and feasible search strategy. The results of this preliminary exploration are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2

Pilot testing of GAD-7 instrument terms in Google Scholar and PubMed

Terminologies	Google Scholar	PubMed
GAD-7	64,200	116,442
Generalized Anxiety Disorder-7	2,690,000	2,571
GAD-7 scale	54,400	33,904
GAD-7 questionnaire	57,800	115,039

Development of search strategy:

We searched PubMed databases to review existing studies on the GAD-7 to understand how authors structured their searches, developed search terms, and reported measurement properties, including how and whether they applied frameworks

such as COSMIN and QUADAS. This helped in the development of our initial COSMIN-informed search strategy.

Pilot search equation

Based on this exploratory assessment, a structured search strategy was developed using the COSMIN taxonomy of measurement properties and informed by search strings used in a previously published systematic review of measurement properties of another patient-reported outcome measure (Habibi et al., 2024). The draft search strategy combined GAD-7 instrument terms with psychometric and diagnostic accuracy terminology and was piloted in PubMed.

PubMed

#1 ("GAD-7"[tiab] OR GAD7[tiab] OR "Generalized Anxiety Disorder-7"[tiab])

AND

#2 (psychometric*[tiab] OR "Psychometrics"[MeSH Terms] OR reliab*[tiab] OR "test-retest"[tiab] OR "measurement error"[tiab] OR cronbach*[tiab] OR "Reproducibility of Results"[MeSH Terms] OR valid*[tiab] OR "construct"[tiab] OR "structural"[tiab] OR "convergent"[tiab] OR "discriminant"[tiab] OR "known-groups"[tiab] OR "content"[tiab] OR responsiveness[tiab] OR "longitudinal validity"[tiab] OR "item correlation"[tiab] OR "inter-item correlation"[tiab] OR "interitem correlation"[tiab] OR "internal consistency"[tiab] OR sensitivity[tiab] OR specificity[tiab] OR "ROC curve"[tiab])

Pilot screening

The drafted search strategy was tested in PubMed. The pilot search retrieved 1,751 records, which was reduced to 1,750 records after duplicate removal. All retrieved records were exported to the EvidenceBee platform for pilot screening (see Figure 1 for the details of the number of results yielded using the search strategy). Title and abstract screening was conducted by two independent reviewers to assess the feasibility, relevance, and clarity of the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Review of the approximately 700 records at the title and abstract level, 366 studies were excluded as they were irrelevant. . 180 records were considered potentially relevant. No full-text eligibility assessment was completed at this stage, as the purpose of the pilot was to test the search strategy and screening procedures rather than to determine final inclusion.

Figure 1. Sample flow diagram of evidence synthesis PRISMA.

Exploratory scoping of studies on measurement properties

The pilot screening confirmed that a substantial proportion of retrieved studies used the GAD-7 without explicitly evaluating its measurement properties, supporting the decision to restrict inclusion to studies that clearly report evaluation of measurement properties using appropriate terminology. In parallel, a preliminary scoping exercise identified five studies explicitly focused on the measurement properties of the GAD-7, for which key characteristics were extracted to further inform refinement of the screening rules.

Scoping review

A preliminary scoping exercise identified five studies explicitly focused on the measurement properties of the GAD-7. For these studies, key information was extracted, including author and year, country/language, population characteristics, age, sample size, gender distribution, study design, measurement properties assessed, main findings, and risk of bias considerations. A detailed extraction is shown in the Table 3.

Table 3

Exploratory scoping summary of five studies on measurement properties of GAD-7

Study (Author, Year)	Setting (Language/Country)	Population	Age (Mean or Range)	Sample Size	Gender Distribution	PROM	Study Design	COSMIN Properties Assessed
Hinz et al., 2016	German/Germany	General adult population	18-80	9,721	5,106 females, 4,615 males	GAD-7/GAD-2	Population-based cohort	Structural validity, internal consistency, construct validity, measurement invariance
Sun et al., 2021	Chinese/China	Adolescents	10-17	67,281	51.9% boys, 48.1% girls	GAD-7 (Chinese version)	Multistage sampling	Structural validity, internal consistency, construct validity
White & Karr, 2023	English/USA	Undergraduate students	Mean 19.0	582	79.4% female	GAD-7	Cross-sectional validation	Internal consistency, structural validity, construct validity, measurement invariance
Bolgeo et al., 2023	Italian/Italy	Adults with CHD	Mean 64.7	398	78.9% male	GAD-7	Cross-sectional secondary analysis	Internal consistency, structural validity, construct validity, measurement invariance
Saracino et al., 2024	English/USA	Older adults with cancer	≥70 (Mean 77.2)	718	57% male	GAD-7	Secondary analysis of trial	Internal consistency, structural validity, construct validity, IRT, cut-off evaluation

Refinement of methods

Based on insights from this pilot work, refinements to the search strategy and screening procedures were made in collaboration with the review team, COSMIN search filters, and research librarians to improve precision while maintaining comprehensive coverage. The finalized search strategy will be applied across all selected databases in the full mapping phase.

Appendix D

Codebook for data extraction Phase A (Living Mapping of the Evidence)

Category	Variable name	Variable definition	Permissible values
Study metadata	DOI	Digital Object Identifier	Alphanumeric DOI string
	Database identifier	Unique identifier assigned to the study by the database in which it is indexed (e.g., PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, Embase)	PMID (numeric), Web of Science Accession Number (alphanumeric), Embase ID (alphanumeric), or another database-specific identifier.
	Author	Surname of the first author of the study	First author surname followed by <i>et al.</i> (if applicable)
	Year of publication	Calendar year in which the study was published	Four-digit year (e.g., 2018)
	Journal	Name of the journal in which the article was published	Alphanumeric
	Article ID	Unique identifier assigned to the article within the review	Review-assigned article ID (Alphanumeric string)
	Sample ID	Unique identifier assigned within the review to each unique sample in the article (if multiple samples)	Review-assigned sample ID Not applicable
Study characteristics	Study methodological approach	Study methodological approach based on the nature of the data collected and the analytic methods used.	Quantitative
			Qualitative
			Mixed-methods

			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Study design	Type of methodological design used in the study	Observational – Cross-sectional
			Observational – Longitudinal Prospective
			Observational – Longitudinal Retrospective
			Observational – Longitudinal (Timing Not Reported)
			Interventional – Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT)
			Interventional – Non-randomized Trial /quasi-experimental
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Inclusion criteria with threshold	Indicate if the participants of the study were included according to a continuous threshold	Yes
			No
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
PROM characteristics	Patient-reported outcome measure (PROM) used	Name of the PROM used in the study that is within the scope of this review (If a study uses more than one eligible PROM, a	GAD7 (7-item anxiety scale)
			PHQ9 (9-item depression scale)
			RCADS 25

		separate data-extraction row will be completed for each PROM)	WHODAS 36-item
			WHODAS 12-item (short form)
			WHODAS 12+24-item
	Scoring computation method (only for WHODAS)	Method used to calculate WHODAS 2.0 scores: simple (unweighted sum), complex (IRT-weighted)	Simple scoring
			Complex scoring
			Not applicable
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Item wording modifications	Indicate whether the item wording has been modified from the original validated version of the instrument	Yes
			No
	Detail item wording modifications	Specify which changes were made to the item wording	Alphanumeric string
			Not applicable
	Response scoring modifications	Indicate whether the response scoring has been modified from the original validated version of the instrument	Yes
			No
	Detail response scoring modifications	Specify which changes were made to the response scoring	Alphanumeric string
			Not applicable
Other PROM 1	Name of other instrument used in the study (to be completed if the study assessed any measurement property of another listed	GAD2 (2-item anxiety screener)	
		PHQ2 (2-item depression screener)	

	instrument in addition to the main eligible PROM)	PHQ4 (4-item combined anxiety/depression screener)	
		PHQ5 (5-item short form)	
		PHQ8 (8-item depression scale (no suicidality item))	
		RCADS 11	
		RCADS 25	
		RCADS 47	
		WHODAS 36-item	
		WHODAS 12-item (short form)	
		WHODAS 12+24-item	
		Other (specify)	
		Not applicable	
	Other PROM 1 (other)	Specify the name of the instrument when "Other (specify)" is selected for the variable Other PROM 1	Alphanumeric string
			Not applicable
Other PROM 2	Name of other instrument used in the study (to be completed if the study assessed any measurement property of another listed instrument in addition to the main eligible PROM)	GAD2 (2-item anxiety screener)	
		PHQ2 (2-item depression screener)	
		PHQ4 (4-item combined anxiety/depression screener)	
		PHQ5 (5-item short form)	

			PHQ8 (8-item depression scale (no suicidality item))
			RCADS 11
			RCADS 25
			RCADS 47
			WHODAS 36-item
			WHODAS 12-item (short form)
			WHODAS 12+24-item
			Other (specify)
			Not applicable
	Other PROM 2 (other)	Specify the name of the instrument when "Other (specify)" is selected for the variable Other PROM 2	Alphanumeric string
			Not applicable
	Administration mode	Mode of administration indicating the informant of the scale	Self-reported version
			Caregiver report version (RCADS only)
			Interviewer version eliciting patient perspective
Completion assistance	If the respondent requires assistance to complete the scale (without judgement or influence of the person assisting the application of the instrument), which type of assistance is provided to the target individual (informant) during completion of the scale	No assistance	
		Interviewer-assisted	
		Caregiver-assisted	
		Clinician-assisted	

			Other (specify)
	Completion assistance (other)	Description of the type of completion assistance when “Other (specify)” is selected for the variable Completion assistance	Alphanumeric string
			Not applicable
	Medium of administration	Format or medium used to deliver the scale	Paper and pencil
			Digital device (any)
			Telephone interview
			Other (specify)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don’t know/don’t understand
	Medium of administration (other)	Description of the medium of administration when “Other (specify)” is selected for the variable Medium of administration	Alphanumeric string
			Not applicable
	Purpose of using the scale	Context of use of the PROM in which the measurement properties were evaluated	Diagnostic/screening
			Outcome assessment
			Other (specify)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don’t know/don’t understand
	Language	Language in which the PROM is administered (as reported in the article)	Alphanumeric string
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don’t know/don’t understand

Participants' characteristics	Description of the study sample	Description of the included study sample as shown in the article	Alphanumeric string
	Age group of the study sample	Age category of the study sample as reported in the article, based on the age range or mean age of participants	Adults
			Adolescents
			Adults and adolescents
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Sample size	Total number of participants included in the study/analysis	Integer value (N)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Minimum age (inclusion criteria)	Lower eligible age threshold	Age in years
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Maximum age (inclusion criteria)	Upper eligible age threshold	Age in years
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Minimum age (study sample)	Youngest age among participants included in the study	Age in years
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand

	Maximum age (study sample)	Oldest age among participants included in the study	Age in years
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Mean age of the study sample	Mean (average) age of the study sample	Numeric value (years)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Age standard deviation of the study sample	Standard deviation of age within the study sample	Numeric value (years)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Median age of the study sample	Median age within the study sample	Numeric value (years)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Number of male participants	Total number of male participants included in the study	Integer value (N)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Number of female participants	Total number of female participants included in the study	Integer value (N)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand

	Sex distribution	Percentage of study participants who are female, as reported or calculable from the study (use the proportion reported by the authors or calculate it from provided sex distribution data when available)	Alphanumeric string. Percentage of male and female participants
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Gender distribution	Percentage of participants categorized by gender identity (e.g., man, woman, non-binary), if defined or implied in the study, based on self-identification or explicit gender measures	Alphanumeric string. Percentage of participants self-identified as man, woman, non-binary or other (specify the percentage for each reported gender).
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Type of population	General classification of the population studied	Clinical (physical health conditions)
			Clinical (mental health conditions)
			Clinical (substance-use disorders)
			Healthy volunteer (with no diagnosed conditions)
			General population (community sample)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
Category physical health condition 1	Primary category describing the physical health condition present in the study population, if applicable	Cardiovascular diseases (e.g., hypertension, coronary artery disease, heart failure, stroke)	

			Metabolic and endocrine disorders (e.g., diabetes, obesity, metabolic syndrome, thyroid disorders)
			Respiratory diseases (e.g., asthma, COPD)
			Neurological disorders (non-psychiatric) (e.g., Parkinson's disease, multiple sclerosis, epilepsy, migraine)
			Musculoskeletal conditions (e.g., arthritis, chronic back pain, osteoporosis)
			Chronic pain conditions (e.g., fibromyalgia, chronic low back pain, neuropathic pain)
			Cancer / oncological conditions
			Autoimmune and inflammatory diseases (e.g., rheumatoid arthritis, lupus, inflammatory bowel disease)
			Gastrointestinal diseases (e.g., IBS, Crohn's disease, ulcerative colitis)
			Renal and urological diseases
			Chronic infectious diseases (e.g., HIV, hepatitis)
			Sensory impairments (e.g., visual or hearing impairment)
			Other physical health condition
			Unclear – lack of reporting

			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Name of the physical health condition 1	Specific physical health diagnosis or condition present in the study population, as reported by the authors	Alphanumeric string (e.g., Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Diagnostic basis physical health condition 1	Method used to determine the presence of the physical health condition among participants	Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis)
			Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., ICD, ADA guidelines)
			Self-reported diagnosis
			Screening tool
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Definition physical health condition 1	Operational or clinical definition of the physical health condition used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions	Alphanumeric string
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
Not applicable			

	<p>Category physical health condition 2</p>	<p>Primary category describing an additional physical health condition present in the study population when multiple physical conditions are reported as comorbidities. If measurement properties are evaluated separately for different diseases using distinct participant samples, a separate data-extraction row will be completed for each health condition.</p>	<p>Cardiovascular diseases (e.g., hypertension, coronary artery disease, heart failure, stroke)</p> <p>Metabolic and endocrine disorders (e.g., diabetes, obesity, metabolic syndrome, thyroid disorders)</p> <p>Respiratory diseases (e.g., asthma, COPD)</p> <p>Neurological disorders (non-psychiatric) (e.g., Parkinson's disease, multiple sclerosis, epilepsy, migraine)</p> <p>Musculoskeletal conditions (e.g., arthritis, chronic back pain, osteoporosis)</p> <p>Chronic pain conditions (e.g., fibromyalgia, chronic low back pain, neuropathic pain)</p> <p>Cancer / oncological conditions</p> <p>Autoimmune and inflammatory diseases (e.g., rheumatoid arthritis, lupus, inflammatory bowel disease)</p> <p>Gastrointestinal diseases (e.g., IBS, Crohn's disease, ulcerative colitis)</p> <p>Renal and urological diseases</p> <p>Chronic infectious diseases (e.g., HIV, hepatitis)</p> <p>Sensory impairments (e.g., visual or hearing impairment)</p>
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			Other physical health condition
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Name of the physical health condition 2	Specific physical health diagnosis or condition present in the study population, as reported by the authors	Alphanumeric string (e.g., Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Diagnostic basis physical health condition 2	Method used to determine the presence of the physical health condition among participants	Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis)
			Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., ICD, ADA guidelines)
			Self-reported diagnosis
			Screening tool
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Definition physical health condition 2	Operational or clinical definition of the physical health condition used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment	Alphanumeric string
Unclear – lack of reporting			

		tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions	Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Category physical health condition 3	Primary category describing an additional physical health condition present in the study population when multiple physical conditions are reported as comorbidities. If measurement properties are evaluated separately for different diseases using distinct participant samples, a separate data-extraction row will be completed for each health condition	Cardiovascular diseases (e.g., hypertension, coronary artery disease, heart failure, stroke)
			Metabolic and endocrine disorders (e.g., diabetes, obesity, metabolic syndrome, thyroid disorders)
			Respiratory diseases (e.g., asthma, COPD)
			Neurological disorders (non-psychiatric) (e.g., Parkinson's disease, multiple sclerosis, epilepsy, migraine)
			Musculoskeletal conditions (e.g., arthritis, chronic back pain, osteoporosis)
			Chronic pain conditions (e.g., fibromyalgia, chronic low back pain, neuropathic pain)
			Cancer / oncological conditions
			Autoimmune and inflammatory diseases (e.g., rheumatoid arthritis, lupus, inflammatory bowel disease)
			Gastrointestinal diseases (e.g., IBS, Crohn's disease, ulcerative colitis)
			Renal and urological diseases

			Chronic infectious diseases (e.g., HIV, hepatitis)
			Sensory impairments (e.g., visual or hearing impairment)
			Other physical health condition
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Name of the physical health condition 3	Specific physical health diagnosis or condition present in the study population, as reported by the authors	Alphanumeric string (e.g., Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Diagnostic basis physical health condition 3	Method used to determine the presence of the physical health condition among participants	Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis)
			Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., ICD, ADA guidelines)
			Self-reported diagnosis
			Screening tool
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand

			Not applicable
	Definition physical health condition 3	Operational or clinical definition of the physical health condition used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions	Alphanumeric string
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Category mental health condition 1	Primary category describing the mental health condition present in the study population, if applicable	Depressive disorders (e.g., major depressive disorder, dysthymia)
			Anxiety disorders (e.g., generalized anxiety disorder, panic disorder, phobias)
			Stress-related and trauma-related disorders (e.g., PTSD, adjustment disorder)
			Bipolar and related disorders
			Psychotic disorders (e.g., schizophrenia, schizoaffective disorder)
			Neurodevelopmental disorders (e.g., ADHD, autism spectrum disorder)
			Eating disorders (e.g., anorexia nervosa, bulimia nervosa, binge-eating disorder)
			Personality disorders
			Cognitive disorders / dementia
			Sleep-wake disorders (e.g., insomnia)
			Other mental health condition

			Unclear – lack of reporting	
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand	
			Not applicable	
	Name of the mental health condition 1	Specific mental health diagnosis or condition present in the study population, as reported by the authors		Alphanumeric string (e.g., major depressive disorder)
				Unclear – lack of reporting
				Unclear – don't know/don't understand
				Not applicable
	Diagnostic basis mental health condition 1	Method used to determine the presence of the mental health condition among participants		Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis)
				Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., DSM, ICD)
				Self-reported diagnosis
				Screening tool
				Unclear – lack of reporting
				Unclear – don't know/don't understand
				Not applicable
	Definition mental health condition 1	Operational or clinical definition of the mental health condition used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions		Alphanumeric string
Unclear – lack of reporting				
Unclear – don't know/don't understand				

			Not applicable
	Category mental health condition 2	Primary category describing an additional mental health condition present in the study population when multiple mental health conditions are reported as comorbidities. If measurement properties are evaluated separately for different diseases using distinct participant samples, a separate data-extraction row will be completed for each health condition	Depressive disorders (e.g., major depressive disorder, dysthymia)
			Anxiety disorders (e.g., generalized anxiety disorder, panic disorder, phobias)
			Stress-related and trauma-related disorders (e.g., PTSD, adjustment disorder)
			Bipolar and related disorders
			Psychotic disorders (e.g., schizophrenia, schizoaffective disorder)
			Neurodevelopmental disorders (e.g., ADHD, autism spectrum disorder)
			Eating disorders (e.g., anorexia nervosa, bulimia nervosa, binge-eating disorder)
			Personality disorders
			Cognitive disorders / dementia
			Sleep-wake disorders (e.g., insomnia)
			Other mental health condition
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable

	Name of the mental health condition 2	Specific mental health diagnosis or condition present in the study population, as reported by the authors	Alphanumeric string (e.g., major depressive disorder)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Diagnostic basis mental health condition 2	Method used to determine the presence of the mental health condition among participants	Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis)
			Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., DSM, ICD)
			Self-reported diagnosis
			Screening tool
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Definition mental health condition 2	Operational or clinical definition of the mental health condition used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions	Alphanumeric string
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Category mental health condition 3	Primary category describing an additional mental health condition present in the study	Depressive disorders (e.g., major depressive disorder, dysthymia)

		<p>population when multiple mental health conditions are reported as comorbidities. If measurement properties are evaluated separately for different diseases using distinct participant samples, a separate data-extraction row will be completed for each health condition</p>	Anxiety disorders (e.g., generalized anxiety disorder, panic disorder, phobias)
			Stress-related and trauma-related disorders (e.g., PTSD, adjustment disorder)
			Bipolar and related disorders
			Psychotic disorders (e.g., schizophrenia, schizoaffective disorder)
			Neurodevelopmental disorders (e.g., ADHD, autism spectrum disorder)
			Eating disorders (e.g., anorexia nervosa, bulimia nervosa, binge-eating disorder)
			Personality disorders
			Cognitive disorders / dementia
			Sleep-wake disorders (e.g., insomnia)
			Other mental health condition
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
			Name of the mental health condition 3
Unclear – lack of reporting			
Unclear – don't know/don't understand			

			Not applicable
	Diagnostic basis mental health condition 3	Method used to determine the presence of the mental health condition among participants	Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis) Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., DSM, ICD) Self-reported diagnosis Screening tool Unclear – lack of reporting Unclear – don't know/don't understand Not applicable
	Definition mental health condition 3	Operational or clinical definition of the mental health condition used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions	Alphanumeric string Unclear – lack of reporting Unclear – don't know/don't understand Not applicable
	Category substance-use disorder 1	Primary category describing the substance-use disorder present in the study population, if applicable	Alcohol use disorder Tobacco / nicotine use disorder Cannabis use disorder Opioid use disorder Stimulant use disorder (e.g., cocaine, amphetamines, methamphetamine)

			Sedative, hypnotic, or anxiolytic use disorder
			Polysubstance use disorder
			Other substance-use disorder
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Name of the substance-use disorder 1	Specific substance-use disorder present in the study population, as reported by the authors	Alphanumeric string (e.g., alcohol abuse disorder)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Diagnostic basis substance-use disorder 1	Method used to determine the presence of the substance-use disorder among participants	Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis)
			Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., DSM, ICD)
			Self-reported diagnosis
			Screening tool
			Unclear – lack of reporting
Unclear – don't know/don't understand			
Not applicable			

	Definition substance-use disorder 1	Operational or clinical definition of the substance-use disorder used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions	Alphanumeric string
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Category substance-use disorder 2	Primary category describing an additional substance-use disorder present in the study population when multiple substance-use disorders are reported as coexistent. If measurement properties are evaluated separately for different substance-use disorders using distinct participant samples, a separate data-extraction row will be completed for each disorder	Alcohol use disorder
			Tobacco / nicotine use disorder
			Cannabis use disorder
			Opioid use disorder
			Stimulant use disorder (e.g., cocaine, amphetamines, methamphetamine)
			Sedative, hypnotic, or anxiolytic use disorder
			Polysubstance use disorder
			Other substance-use disorder
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Not applicable		
Name of the substance-use disorder 2	Specific substance-use disorder present in the study population, as reported by the authors	Alphanumeric string (e.g., alcohol abuse disorder)	
		Unclear – lack of reporting	
		Unclear – don't know/don't understand	

			Not applicable
	Diagnostic basis substance-use disorder 2	Method used to determine the presence of the substance-use disorder among participants	Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis) Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., DSM, ICD) Self-reported diagnosis Screening tool Unclear – lack of reporting Unclear – don't know/don't understand Not applicable
	Definition substance-use disorder 2	Operational or clinical definition of the substance-use disorder used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions	Alphanumeric string Unclear – lack of reporting Unclear – don't know/don't understand Not applicable
	Category substance-use disorder 3	Primary category describing an additional substance-use disorder present in the study population when multiple substance-use disorders are reported as coexistent. If measurement properties are evaluated separately for different substance-use disorders using distinct participant samples, a separate data-extraction row will be completed for each disorder	Alcohol use disorder Tobacco / nicotine use disorder Cannabis use disorder Opioid use disorder Stimulant use disorder (e.g., cocaine, amphetamines, methamphetamine)

			Sedative, hypnotic, or anxiolytic use disorder
			Polysubstance use disorder
			Other substance-use disorder
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Name of the substance-use disorder 3	Specific substance-use disorder present in the study population, as reported by the authors	Alphanumeric string (e.g., alcohol abuse disorder)
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Diagnostic basis substance-use disorder 3	Method used to determine the presence of the substance-use disorder among participants	Clinical diagnosis (medical record / clinician diagnosis)
			Standardized diagnostic criteria (e.g., DSM, ICD)
			Self-reported diagnosis
			Screening tool
			Unclear – lack of reporting
Unclear – don't know/don't understand			
Not applicable			

	Definition substance-use disorder 3	Operational or clinical definition of the substance-use disorder used in the study, including diagnostic criteria, assessment tools, thresholds, or author-provided descriptions	Alphanumeric string
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Specific demographics	Identification of specific demographic subgroups targeted in the study	Veterans
			LGBTQIA+
			Migrants
			Other (specify)
	Geographical setting	Geographic location where the study was conducted	Country or countries
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Healthcare setting level	Level of healthcare system in which the study was conducted	Primary care
			Secondary care
			Tertiary care
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
	Patient setting	Care context in which participants received services or were studied	Outpatient
			Inpatient

			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Not applicable
PROM construct and assessed measurement properties in the study	PROM construct	Construct that the PROM is intended to assess, as explicitly stated by the study authors	Alphanumeric string. Construct description using authors' wording (e.g., quality of life, physical functioning, pain intensity, mental health, symptom severity, etc.)
	Content validity*	The degree to which the content of a PROM is an adequate reflection of the construct to be measured.	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Structural validity*	The degree to which the scores of a PROM are an adequate reflection of the dimensionality of the construct to be measured.	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Internal consistency*	The degree of the interrelatedness among the items.	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
			Yes – reported results

	Cross-cultural validity / measurement invariance*	The degree to which the performance of the items on a translated or culturally adapted PROM are an adequate reflection of the performance of the items of the original version of the PROM.	Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Reliability*	The extent to which scores for respondents who have not changed are the same for repeated measurement under several conditions: e.g., using different sets of items from the same PROM (internal consistency); over time (test-retest); by different persons on the same occasion (inter-rater); or by the same persons (i.e., raters or responders) on different occasions (intra-rater).	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Measurement error*	The systematic and random error of a respondent's score that is not attributed to true changes in the construct to be measured.	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Criterion validity*	Criterion validity refers to the degree to which PROM scores are an adequate reflection of a reference standard (gold standard).	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Comparator instrument for criterion validity	If results for criterion validity are reported, specify which instrument has been used as comparator	Alphanumeric string.
			Not applicable

	Hypothesis testing for construct validity*	The degree to which the scores of a PROM are consistent with hypotheses (with regard to relationships to scores of other instruments, or differences between relevant groups) based on the assumption that the PROM validly measures the construct to be measured.	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Comparator instrument for hypothesis testing for construct validity	If results for hypothesis testing for construct validity are reported, specify which instrument has been used as comparator	Alphanumeric string.
			Not applicable
	Responsiveness*	The ability of a PROM to detect change over time in the construct to be measured.	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
Unclear – lack of reporting			
Unclear – don't know/don't understand			
Comparator instrument for Responsiveness	If results for Responsiveness are reported, specify which instrument has been used as comparator	Alphanumeric string.	
		Not applicable	
Other properties of the measurement tools	Feasibility*	Ease of application of the PROM in its intended context of use, given constraints such as time or money.	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed
			Unclear – lack of reporting
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand
	Interpretability*	The degree to which one can assign qualitative meaning - that is, clinical or commonly understood connotations – to a	Yes – reported results
			Not assessed

		PROM's quantitative scores or change in scores.	Unclear – lack of reporting	
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand	
	Acceptability	How respondents perceive the experience of completing the scale, e.g., perceived intrusiveness, burden, potential harms or benefits.	Yes – reported results	
			Not assessed	
			Unclear – lack of reporting	
			Unclear – don't know/don't understand	
	Involvement of lived-experience contributors	Involvement of lived-experience contributors	Indicate whether individuals with lived experience actively contributed to the study.	Yes
				No
Unclear – lack of reporting				
Unclear – don't know/don't understand				

* Definition derived from the COSMIN taxonomy, as specified in the COSMIN 2.0 guidelines (Mokkink et al., 2024).